

COcyber Cybersphere Insights – October 2025

As Europe's cybersecurity landscape evolves, [COcyber](#) continues to connect civilian and defence actors through evidence-based insights, strategic dialogue, and community-driven collaboration. This edition highlights new progress within the project – from the **new deliverable *Guidelines on Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation*** and our upcoming event in Brussels to updates from the **COcyber platform and Ambassador Programme** – alongside selected insights from the wider European cybersecurity field.

COCYBER UPDATES

COcyber Ambassadors Batch 3 – Call for Expressions of Interest. After welcoming [our first ambassadors](#) in January and a [second group in June 2025](#), COcyber has seen how powerful [this initiative](#) is in **connecting cybersecurity professionals across Europe**. Our ambassadors have played a central role in promoting COcyber's results, supporting events and publications, and amplifying collaboration between civilian and defence communities.

We are now opening the final round for Batch 3, running from December 2025 to May 2026. This is the last opportunity to join a network of experts who share knowledge, build visibility, and shape the project's lasting impact as it enters its final phase.

Express interest: contact@cocyber.eu

[Find out more](#)

DELIVERABLES AND TOOLS

[Deliverable D4.1 – Guidelines on Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation](#). Led by Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB) with contributions from IVSZ and INFOBALT, Deliverable D4.1 **gathers evidence on how Europe’s civilian and defence sectors can cooperate more effectively**. Drawing on more than 600 sources and 11 validated best practices, the report proposes seven strategic guidelines to enhance collaboration – from shared threat-intelligence frameworks to harmonised governance, joint training, and interoperability.

The cover of the report features a blue and green background with a pattern of interconnected circles. At the top left is the European Union flag and the text "Funded by the European Union". At the top center is the "coccyber" logo. At the top right is the ECCC logo (European Cybersecurity Competence Centre). The main title "Deliverable 4.1 Guidelines on Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation" is in large white font. Below it is the subtitle "Bridging Europe’s civilian & defence cybersecurity sectors". A paragraph of text describes the report's content: "The report identifies and validates a set of best practices to enhance cooperation between the civilian and defence cybersecurity communities across Europe. It provides strategic guidelines to foster information sharing, joint preparedness, and a resilient European cybersecurity ecosystem".

[Read the full deliverable](#)

[COcyber Platform – Explore the COcyber Map.](#) The COcyber Map is a key feature of the project’s platform, offering an interactive overview of Europe’s cybersecurity landscape. It brings together **data on funding, procurement, digital skills, and R&I projects**, turning scattered information into a single, accessible tool for decision-makers.

With 71 indicators and a transparent, research-based methodology, the [Map](#) allows users to track national trends, benchmark policies, and spot emerging areas for collaboration across the EU. It’s a practical instrument for policymakers, researchers, and industry professionals working to strengthen Europe’s collective cyber resilience.

COcyber Map

What is this map? ▾

Share of Cybersecurity projects across participating countries

Source: Multiple sources (see the Methodological Note) - Reference year: 2001-2025 No data is available for 2002-2004

[Explore the map](#)

[Check the Methodological note](#)

UPCOMING EVENT

Civilian–Defence Cyber Coordination: Fueling Digital & Defence Innovation through Startups, Scaleups and Corporates

 17 **15 October 2025 | 14:00–18:00 CET**

 Permanent Representation of Estonia to the EU, Brussels

 [Registration link](#)

COcyber will join the launch of [EIT Digital's Makers & Shapers Report – Digital & Defence Innovation for Europe's Strategic Autonomy](#) with a dedicated **fireside chat** on the role of cybersecurity in dual-use innovation. Moderated by **COcyber Ambassador Iva Tasheva** (CEO of Cyen) and featuring **Marko Jõemets** (Head of Cybersecurity R&D, Cybernetica AS), the discussion will explore how collaboration between SMEs, start-ups, and corporates accelerates Europe's defence innovation and strengthens resilience to hybrid threats.

FIRESIDE CHAT EVENT

Civilian–Defence Cyber Coordination

Fueling Digital & Defence Innovation through Startups, Scaleups and Corporates

 Speakers
Marko Jõemets Head of Cybersecurity R&D, Cybernetica AS

 Moderator
Iva Tasheva Cyen, CEO – COcyber ambassador

15th October 2025, 14:00–18:00 CET

 Permanent Representation of Estonia to the EU, Brussels

[Register by Friday, October 10th](#)

COCYBER COMMUNITY CALL – SUGGEST AN EVENT

COcyber is building a connected and inclusive European cybersecurity community, bridging civilian and defence perspectives. As part of this effort, **we invite partners, organisations, and experts to share upcoming events that align with our themes**, from cybersecurity innovation and dual-use technologies to policy dialogue, capacity building, and knowledge exchange.

Submitted events are reviewed for relevance and completeness, and once approved, they become visible across the COcyber platform, **helping you reach a wider European network of practitioners and policymakers.**

[Submit your event](#)

NEWS FROM THE FIELD

[Off the Hook – Don't be Phished this Cybersecurity Month.](#) October marks European Cybersecurity Month, the EU's annual campaign led by ENISA and the European Commission to **raise awareness about digital security**. This year's spotlight is on phishing, still the number one entry point for cyberattacks. From *smishing* and *quishing* to deepfake scams and AI-powered phishing, the threats are multiplying fast.

Join the campaign: [Think Before U Click](#)

[ENISA Threat Landscape 2025 is out.](#) Covering nearly 4,900 incidents across Europe, this year's ENISA report captures a cyber environment that is maturing fast — and becoming more complex. From ransomware decentralisation and AI-driven phishing campaigns to state-aligned espionage and the industrialisation of cybercrime, ENISA outlines a picture of convergence: continuous, multi-layered attacks that collectively erode resilience rather than rely on single high-impact events.

[Read the report](#)

[Why cybersecurity's future depends on people, not just technology](#). Published by the World Economic Forum in October 2025, the article reminds us that **even the most advanced digital systems collapse when the people behind them aren't prepared to recognise or respond to threats**. In 2024, 95% of data breaches were traced to human error, showing that the greatest vulnerability is not in machines but in habits, awareness, and decision-making.

Read the [World Economic Forum](#) article

⚡ Don't miss any future COcyber events connecting the dots between civilian and defence cyber security initiatives. Join our community now at <https://cocyber.eu/user/register>

Disclaimer

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